

TYPES OF BOOK GENRES ON THE SCIENCE OF HADITH

Oriental university

associate professor of history department

doctor of philosophy of historical sciences (PhD)

Alijonova Gulnozakhan

In the sources of Islam, the second source after the Qur'an is the collection of hadiths. Reliable collections containing authentic hadiths are one of the most reliable sources for studying the words, manners, verbs, and interpretations of the Prophet (pbuh) and for understanding Islam and putting it into practice. Therefore, many books on the science of hadith have been written by Muslim scholars. These books are divided into «Rivayat al-Hadith» and «Dirayat al-Hadith» series.

«Rivayat al-Hadith» books. Since the time of our Prophet (pbuh), the activity of determining hadiths orally and in writing has encouraged Muslims to do various researches, and in the first centuries of Hijri, the needs of easier use of hadith texts and the ability to quickly reach the desired hadith made it necessary to write books in different ways. The collection of these methods is called «narration al-hadith». In this direction, the following genres served as a basis:

1) Books - after the collection of hadiths was completed, they began to be classified according to the subject or the names of the narrators. Some parts of the works classified according to topics such as «Kutubi Sitta» such as «Iman», «Ilm» and «Etiquette» are written by the Muhaddiths of the first period, and sometimes the «Jome» and «Sunan» were written as separate works by the scholars. it is called «book». Books in this category include «Kitab al-zuhd wa ar-raqaiq» by Abdullah ibn Mubarak (d. 181/797), «Kitab al-iman» by Abu Ubayd Qasim (d. 224/838) and similar books.

2) Musnads - their main feature is that the hadiths are arranged according to the names of the companions, regardless of their topic, authenticity or weakness. «Musnad Abu Bakr Siddiq» of Marwazi (d. 292/905), «Musnad» of Abdullah ibn Mubarak, «Musnad» of Imam Shafi'i (767-820) and other authors are the musnads.

3) Mojamlar is one of the types of books arranged according to the names of the narrators. In Mojam, the narrations are written in alphabetical order either by the names of the Companions, like the Musnads, or by the names of the teachers of the Muhaddis. «Mojam» by Abu Yala Mawsuli (d. 307/919), «Mojam» by Abu Said ibn Arabi (d. 341/952), «Al-mojam» by Tabari (d. 360/971) Al-Awsat»i and other similar temples belong to this category.

4) Musannaf - books classified under headings according to their subject from the middle of the II/VIII century, some of them were called «jame», but because they had the same classification system, they got the name «musannaf». Works of this genre include «Al-Muwatta» by Malik ibn Anas (d. 179/795), «Al-musannaf fi al-hadith» by Abdurazzaq San'ani (d. 211/826).

5) Jamelar is a type of classification that is required to cover all the issues stated in the hadiths and includes eight main topics and is usually organized according to chapters, which include the Sahihs of Imam Bukhari and Imam Muslim and other works.

6) Sunan and ahkam - the main feature of these books is that the hadiths are arranged in the fiqh al-hadith method. «Kitabi as-sunan fi-fiqh» by Avzai (d. 157/774), «As-sunan fi ma'sura» by Imam Shafi'i, «Sunan» by Sa'd ibn Mansur (d. 227/842) and similar books belong to this category.

7) Mustadraklar - refers to hadiths that are not included in the books that contain authentic hadiths because some of their conditions do not match. These hadiths were collected by the scholars of the next century and these works were called «Mustadrak». Hakim Nishapuri's (d. 405/1014) «Mustadrak al-sahihayn»,

Zahabi's (d. 748/1348) «Mukhtasar al-mustadrak» and other works belong to this category.

8) Mustakhrajlar - the word «istikhraj» which means «extraction» in the dictionary means «narrating all the narrations in the author's book of hadith along with other documents that came to him.» The book containing these hadiths is called «Mustakraj», and the author who performs this work is called «Mustakraj». «Al-Musnad al-mukhraj ala kitabi Muslim ibn Hajjaj» by Abu Awana Isfarani (d. 316/929), «Al-Musnad al-sahih ala kitabi Muslim» by Jawzaqi (d. 388/998) and similar books belong to this category.

9) Forty hadiths - the book of forty hadiths, known as «arba'in», began to be written in the first centuries of the Hijri under the influence of a weak hadith that encourages the memorization of forty hadiths. «Kitab al-arba'» by Hasan ibn Sufyan (d. 303/916), «Kitab al-arba'ina hadith» by Abu Bakr Ajurri (d. 360/970) and the like belong to this group.

10) Surroundings is the plural of the word «side» and means «edge, corner, side of something». From the last quarter of the second century of Hijri, a part of the hadith was written from the beginning to be remembered in the hadith classes and was called «atraf». «Atraf al-sahihayn» by Khalaf Wasiti (d. 401/1010), «Tuhfat al-ashraf bi marifat al-atraf» by Abdurrahman Mizzi (d. 742/1341) and other works belong to this genre.

11) Tahrijs are written in order to determine the level of authenticity of narrations mentioned in some books of tafsir, fiqh, kalam, Sufism and hadith, but the source is not indicated, and to show to whom the narrations belong. «Kitab al-takhrij al-hadith al-ilm» by Husayn al-Bayhaqi (d. 458/1066), «Talhis al-khabar fi tahriji al-hadisi ar-raffiiy al» by Ibn Hajar Asqalani (d. 852/1449) «Kabir» pamphlet and other books belong to this category.

12) Zawaidlar - the word «zawaid» which is the plural of the word «zoid» in the dictionary, which means «excess», «more», «additional» in the science of

hadith, is one or more hadith books refer to works that collect hadiths that are more or different from the main books. Mawsuli's «Majmu'a az-zawaid wa manba al-fawaid», Ibn Hajar Asqalani's «Al-Matalib al-aliya bi zawaidi al-musanidi al-samaniyya» and similar works belong to this category.

13) Fawoid - although the word «fawoid» is used in the sense of «a book that collects useful information on the subject», muhaddis or various scholars in hadith science are mostly individual (in some parts of the narration, the number of narrators is odd, the term used for a lost hadith) and gharib (a hadith in which the number of narrators falls to one in any part of the narration) are collections of narrations. The work of Abu Bakr Shafi'i (d. 354/965) «Al-Ghaylaniyat diya mashruh al-fawaid al-muntahabat al-awail ani ash-shuyuh» and similar works belong to this category.

14) Practitioners - muhaddiths, commentators, jurists, scholars of Arabic language and literature, and some other scholars ordered their students to memorize hadiths within the scope of their subject, and sometimes to copy them with their sanads. Although the books of hadith are classified according to the names of the narrators in the musnads and the topics in the sunnah and mosques, this order is not usually observed in the works. The books «al-Amoli» by Imam Abu Yusuf (d. 182/798), «Juz min al-amoli» by Muhammad Shaybani (d. 189/805) and the like belong to this type.

15) Shamail - this word, meaning «custom», «nature», «verb», «morality» in the dictionary, is used in works on poetry, history and mysticism, especially on the science of hadith, from the III/IX century. found in books, applied to books that describe the appearance, personal life and manners of the Prophet (pbuh). The book «Shamoili Muhammadiyya» by Termizi (d. 279/892), «Sharhi Shamoili Nabavi» by Qastalani (d. 923/1517) and the like were written in this genre.

«Dirayat al-Hadith» - the works of this genre are broader than the science of «Rivayat al-Hadith» and are analyzed together with the isnads of hadiths. It

also determines which of the hadiths of the Prophet (pbuh) meet the criteria of sahih, hasan and weak, and determines how reliable their narrators are. The most famous hadith collections related to this category are:

1) Usul al-Hadith is the science of hadith method, which forms the basis of «Dirayat al-Hadith» and is also known as «mustalah al-Hadith» and «Ulum al-Hadith». Hakim Nishopuri's «Ma'rifat al-ulum al-hadith», Khatib Baghdadi's (d. 1391/1971) «al-Kifaya fi ilmi ar-rawi» books and others belong to this category.

2) Rijal al-hadith are books used to determine the narrators of hadith science and their level of reliability, such as «Zikru min yu'tamadu qawluhu fi al-jarh wa ta'dil» by Zahabi, «al-Mutakallimuna fi rijal» by Abdurrahman Sahavi ” books and the like belong to this group.

3) Hadith science - includes the methods and methods used by muhaddiths to check the level of reliability of hadiths and accept them.

The following conclusions were drawn from the research carried out in the 19th and 20th centuries using "Kutubi sitta" books:

First of all, the researches on "Kutubi-sitta" collections carried out in the XIX-XX centuries were carried out mainly by Orientalists (Orientalists) in the West, while in the East they were researched more by religious scholars.

Secondly, the opinions presented in the research conducted by Western orientalists, especially I. Goldziher, regarding the unreliability of "Kutubi Sitta" do not have a scientific basis, and the muhaddiths, who are the authors of the works in the Collections, are very strict in accepting hadiths. and that he observed perfect order for his time was not sufficiently and impartially appreciated.

Thirdly, the researches of "Kutubi sitta" carried out by oriental scientists in the 19th and 20th centuries mainly consisted of protecting these books and strengthening their previous level. Rezauddin ibn Fakhriddin also published the work "Qutubi Sitta and Authors" with this task in mind. In turn, this work was widely distributed in the scientific circles of Tsarist Russia, especially in

Turkestan, in the 20th century, and served as one of the important sources for people to study the science of hadith and the history of muhaddis.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED

1. Al-Xattobiy. Muallimu as-Sunan. – Bayrut: Dor al-kutub al-ilmiyya, 1996. – 302 b.
2. Al-Hakim. Ma’rifatu ulumil hadis. – Bayrut: Dor al-kutub al-ilmiyya, 2016. – 304 b.
3. Al-Hakim. Al-Mustadrak ala as-sahihayn. – Bayrut: Dor al-kutub al-ilmiyya, 1990. V jild. – 3464 b.
4. Al-Hakam. Al-Madhal. – Bayrut: Dor al-kutub al-ilmiyya, 1984. – 454 b.
5. Al-Havli. Tarixi fununil hadisi an-Nabaviy. – Bayrut: Dorul ibn Kasir, 1988. – 374 b.
6. Al-Iroqiy. Fath al-mug’is sharhi al-fiyyat al-hadis. Bayrut: Dor al-kutub al-ilmiyya, 2011. – 472 b.
7. An-Navaviy. Sahihu Muslim bi sharhi an-Navaviy (Muqaddima). – Bayrut: Darul ilahiyat turasil arabiy, 1972. VI jild. – 17600 b.
8. As-Sahaviy. Fathul mug’is sharhi alfiyatil hadis. – Bayrut: Dor al-kutub al-ilmiyya, 1996. – 660 b.